

I. Introduction

The BIM Dictionary (BIMdictionary.com) is a knowledgebase covering of information management and performance improvement concepts necessary to enable digital transformation in the Built Environment. The BIM Dictionary is part of the **BIMe Initiative** (BIMeI – BIMexcellence.org) and its mission¹ is to facilitate digital transformation across the Built Environment by promoting shared goals, encouraging knowledge exchange, and enabling a common language across sectors, disciplines, and language barriers.

To achieve this mission, the BIM Dictionary collates hundreds of interlinked terms, their descriptions, and translations² to achieve the following objectives:

1. Provide a trusted peer-reviewed knowledge source for learners, professionals, and researchers alike;
2. Deliver, expand, and maintain an intuitive digital knowledgebase for all to freely access and benefit from. The knowledgebase can be referenced by digital documents (e.g. agreements & appointments), embedded into websites, and integrated into learning/training materials;
3. Offer a version-controlled and quality-checked dataset for solution developers to rely on for developing open-access digital guides and tools³; and
4. Integrate the deliverables of all BIMe Initiative projects by connecting [Dictionary Items](#) to other key lists with the BIMe Initiative (e.g. [Competency Items](#), and [Model Uses](#)).

Reflecting the mission and objectives, the BIM Dictionary Logo (updated Sep 2019) includes three overlapping symbols representing the interplay of Knowledge, Language, and Network:

- The *book symbol* represents the BIM Dictionary's research foundations, knowledge content, and the encyclopedic nature of its extended descriptions;
- The *speech bubble symbol* represents the common language the BIM Dictionary promotes to enable communication and knowledge-sharing; and
- The *nodes symbol* represents the connections between terms, languages, and the centrality of the BIM Dictionary among other BIMe Initiative resources and tools.

The BIM Dictionary is a foundational project of the **BIMe Initiative**⁴, a not-for-profit community effort aiming to improve industry's digital performance through high-impact research, free online tools, and open knowledge-sharing. Based on **peer-reviewed publications** and a set of **principles**⁵, the BIMe Initiative offers a set of interconnected knowledge resources and open-access tools for all to freely use and continuously improve. The BIMe Initiative (BIMeI) is undertaken by a community of subject matter experts from both industry and academia⁶. BIMeI projects are reliant on the generous efforts of volunteers and are maintained through institutional support, and corporate [sponsorship](#). To learn more about the BIMe Initiative, its community, projects, and resources, please visit BIMexcellence.org.

¹ Mission statement has been updated on Aug 1, 2019.

² For more information covering how terms are chosen, please refer to: <https://bimdictionary.com/basics/>.

³ Commercial uses of the BIM Dictionary are subject to licensing arrangements. Proceeds generated from such licensing will be exclusively used to support the expansion of the knowledgebase across the BIMe Initiative.

⁴ The BIM Dictionary was first launched in December 2012 as part of BIM Excellence Corporate Services (BIMexcellence.com) and, in April 2016, transferred to the not-for-profit BIMe Initiative (BIMexcellence.org).

⁵ BIMe Initiative Principles includes both [General Principles](#) and the [Excellence Manifesto](#).

⁶ The BIM Excellence approach and the BIMe Initiative are based on the published research of [Dr. Bilal Succar](#) and a growing cohort of esteemed international collaborators.

II. BIM Dictionary Roles – List

The BIM Dictionary platform supports numerous roles – users, editors, and curators:

1. Users	Free access to front-end features
1.1. Guest User	Searching and browsing all materials
1.2. Registered User	+ add user notes and create/embed user lists
1.3. Institutional User	+ special features (e.g. allow images, links, and videos in user notes)
2. Editorial Team	Develop strategies and execute plans for continued network and content growth, maintain content quality, and achieve/sustain high levels of engagement with both user and editorial communities
2.1. Head Editor	Overall project management and ensuring project deliverables are well-integrated with other BIMe Initiative projects and resources. The Head Editor is also responsible for the Canonical Language (Australian English) and the maintenance of inclusion/exclusion rules
2.2. Assistant Editor for Community Coordination	Manage the activities and deliverables of Community Coordinators and develop/maintain high levels of engagement with the community
2.3. Assistant Editor for Research & Development	Conduct R&D and testing activities to identify new solutions/integrations, and improve tool accessibility, security, and reliability
2.4. Assistant Editor for Sponsorship and Funding	Identify and pursue opportunities for research funding, instructional support, and corporate funding
3. Community Coordinators	Facilitate the work of the community
3.1. Coordinator for Volunteers and Events	Coordinate the activities of volunteers and take lead in organising community events
3.2. Coordinator for Topic Curation	Coordinate the efforts of Topic Curators and help them connect with Extended Description Authors
3.3. Coordinator for Education, Learning and Training	Engage with learning providers to encourage the adoption of the BIM Dictionary at universities, vocational institutions, and training providers
4. Language Teams	Translate and localise the knowledgebase
4.1. Language Editor (one per language)	Form and manage an Editorial Team of peers to conduct and maintain language translations/localisations. Promote the BIM Dictionary.
4.2. Language Co-Editors	Participate in translating and localising the BIM Dictionary
4.3. Language Reviewer	Review and comment on language translations
5. Country Teams	Provide national context to the knowledgebase
5.1. Country Editor	Add country comments to terms + promote the BIM Dictionary locally
5.2. Country Co-Editor	Participate in adding country comments
5.3. Country Reviewer	Review and improve country comments
6. Topic Teams	Curate specific topics and themes
6.1. Topic Curator (and Reviewer)	Identify terms specific to a 'topic' and identify potential Extended Description Authors
6.2. Extended Description Author	Provide (by invitation) an Extended Description to terms
7. Development Team	Maintaining and improving the online platform
7.1. UX/UI Designers	Front end design and mock-ups
7.2. Full-stack Developers	Front-end and back-end development
7.3. Specialists	Database design, Visualisations, API/SDK and AI/ML
7.4. Code Contributors	Anything that extends the platform

Note: Roles are matched to sets of responsibilities not fully included in this document.

III. Dictionary Item

A Dictionary Item is a term title connected to multiple parts:

Building Information Modelling (BIM) 📄 🔗 ★

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a set of technologies, processes and policies enabling multiple stakeholders to collaboratively design, construct and operate a **Facility** in virtual space. As a term, BIM has grown tremendously over the years and is now the 'current expression of digital innovation' across the construction industry

Similar Terms: Virtual Design and Construction (VDC).

Refer to: Building Information Management.

i Conception
English 🌐

add note

Parts	Example Notes
Term Title	BIM Management Plan the Term Title acts as a link to the Item's own page (See here: https://bimdictionary.com/en/BIM-Management-Plan/1/). Note the URL includes both the Language code "en" according to ISO 639-1 and the version number "1"
Summary Description	The summary description (text only) which may include several Inline Terms . A term's description is typically 80-150 words long
Abbreviation	BMP Abbreviation is searchable and must be unique (no duplication allowed) The abbreviation appears in 'round brackets' after the Term Title
Inline Terms	Inline Terms are contextual links to other terms. They display the linked term's description upon hover/click
Similar Terms	BIM Collaboration Guide Similar terms and are listed under the Summary Description . Similar Terms are unique and searchable
Refer To	Addition terms which may help complete the 'knowledge picture' for the user
Country Flag	Australia This tag is used when the term includes a Country Comment provided by the Country Editor
Language <i>Shown as a code</i>	en fr es Dynamic language selectors that are shown when a Dictionary Item has one or more translation
Labels <i>Mandatory</i>	Each <i>Canonical Term</i> is tagged with at least one 'concept' derived from the BIM Ontology . A label is used as a filter through a drop-down menu. Also, labels appear as 'pills' which – upon click – collate all terms tagged with that label
Info Icon <i>Shown as an icon</i>	The info icon includes the Version and Date and – potentially – author (if applicable). The Info Icon include metadata and usage metrics
Templates <i>Shown as an icon</i>	A Dictionary Item may be extended through a variety of templates, each including additional fields (e.g. extended descriptions rich media, interactive lists, footnotes, acknowledgements, and citation fields). Example templates include "Paper Template" and "Document Template"

IV. Editorial Responsibilities

Below is an overview of the responsibilities of editorial roles. In addition to signing the [Excellence Manifesto](#), detailed responsibilities may be communicated with editors/reviewers/curators when they join the project (including role duration, recommended team configurations, and similar).

A. Language Editors

Language Editors (or LOTE⁷ Editors) have several key responsibilities:

- Form, manage, and motivate an Editorial Team of peers to conduct the language translation.
- Provide translations to canonical Dictionary Items according to priorities set by the Head Editor and an agreed Programme of delivery;
- Ensure translated items are consistent, at high quality and follow the BIM Dictionary's syntax;
- Comply with international standards related to glossaries and thesauri in their language⁸;
- Revise the translated items when canonical items are updated;
- Participate in occasional Editorial Community meetings and communication channels;
- Respond in a timely fashion to BIM Dictionary users' queries and comments;
- Promote their own efforts, the BIM Dictionary, and the BIME Initiative (in their own language) within their professional networks, through social media, and national/international forums; and
- Willing to accept the BIM Dictionary's Terms of Use and – as they need to login and conduct editorial activities online – the Privacy Policy.

B. Language Reviewer

External reviewers may be appointed by the Head Editor (potentially in consultation with the Language/Country Editors) to assess the quality and consistency of the translated items and/or Country Comments. The reviewer is also responsible to check contributions against applicable international standards similar to ISO 25964-1:2011. The External Reviewer can 'Approve for Publication' or request an updated translation from the Editor and Co-Editors. In rare cases where the Reviewer and the Editor cannot agree on a specific translation after several attempts, the Reviewer's comments will be considered as recommendations, and the Editor's decision will be upheld. Reviewers will be adequately acknowledged on the BIM Dictionary Contributors page.

C. Country Editors

Country Editors' main role is to check whether the canonical/translated materials within the BIM Dictionary conform with local standards and to add Country Comments (rich text with links). Country Comments are intended to connect Dictionary Items to national standards and protocols and to clarify terms/descriptions for the local user. Country Editors are selected to represent active national organisations and their efforts are called upon in other BIME Initiative projects (e.g. representing a country in periodical Macro Adoption Studies).

⁷ Language Other Than English (LOTE)

⁸ Language Editors need to review and comply with ISO 25964-1:2011 *Information and documentation — Thesauri and interoperability with other vocabularies Part 1: Thesauri for information retrieval*.

D. Topic Curators

A Topic Curator is responsible for one or more topics within the **BIMe Initiative's Topic Taxonomy**. Curators are selected for their publications or activities in a specific area of expertise. Curators are tasked with:

- Identifying the terms pertaining to their topics for inclusion in the BIM Dictionary;
- Identifying the subject matter experts who can contribute an authoritative extension for terms, and inviting these subject matter experts to contribute according to a Contribution Template;
- Editing contributions to harmonise the content and so it meets publication guidelines;
- Publish, periodically review, and keep-current both terms and extended contributions; and
- Promote their own efforts, the BIM Dictionary, and the BIMe Initiative.

V. Forming a new Editorial Team

The requirements of forming a new Editorial Team will be shared with invited parties. In general, for teams to be formed, they need to be subject-matter experts, gender-diverse, proficient in English, and highly committed to the [principles](#) of the BIMe Initiative.

VI. Editorial Commitments

As the BIM Dictionary is a foundational project - many organisations worldwide are depending on it, and all other BIMe Initiative projects refer to it, it is critically important to continuously extend the BIM Dictionary and improve the quality of its materials. To this end, each Editorial Team will be asked to commit specified editorial efforts that best match the abilities and availability. These commitments will be agreed upon with the Head/Assistant Editors upon commencement of the role and can be revised down at any time. Sample commitments are expressed as (i) *number of items* translated each month, (ii) as a due date for *completing the translation* of a Term Set or the whole dictionary, and/or (iii) as a periodical review/update of LOTE terms to match new or changed canonical items.

VII. Disbanding an Editorial Team

Editors and Curators are free to disband their teams at any time and for any reason by notifying the Head Editor. Also, if a team cannot meet their original or revised commitments, they will be encouraged to expand their team and/or seek assistance from the Editorial Team to identify a suitable way forward. In rare circumstances, and if there are little/no prospects that the Editorial Team will be able to meet their self-imposed commitments, the team may be amicably disbanded, and a new team will be formed.

VIII. Acknowledgement of Contributions

The efforts of all contributors to the BIM Dictionary will be recognised as follows:

- All editors, reviewers and curators' names and affiliation will be listed on the [Contributors](#) page;
- Contributors will be acknowledged when their contributions are used in other BIMeI projects; and
- Contributors who can no longer continue in their role for any reason will also be appropriately acknowledged in a separate section on the same page.

IX. Becoming an Editor

Editors are appointed by invitation or by application. All Editors need to accept the [BIMe Initiative General Principles](#) and are strongly encouraged to sign the [Excellence Manifesto](#). The Head Editor may request to interview potential candidates and seek evidence of domain/language competency (Language Editors must provide evidence of a competent Editorial Team). To be considered for any of the roles, please contact the Head Editor: Dr. Bilal Succar | Email bsuccar@changeagents.com.au or get nominated by a member of the Editorial Team.

X. Language Editor's First Step

Upon appointment, Language Editors are provided with a set of Priority Terms (an Excel File) containing 78 pre-selected items to be translated within 3 months. Once this set has been translated and quality-checked by third parties, it will be uploaded to the online platform. Upon completion of this process, the Editors will identify a suitable translation pace (typically 50 items/month) and additional sets will be released. The Editors and Curators will then receive their credentials enabling them access to the BIM Dictionary platform where they can add/modify terms directly online.

XI. Ongoing Submittal Processes

The Editorial Team will inform all language and country teams of current/future submittal processes. In principle, each team is expected to provide an update every 2 months covering the progress made or lack of. If no update is received for more than 4 months, the Assistant Editor will contact respective Language Editors to resolve any pending issues.

XII. Referencing the BIM Dictionary

The community at large are encouraged to reference the BIM Dictionary. The best method to do so is by embedding a personal Starred List into a website or blog, by embedding the BIM Dictionary Search Bar (once available and where permitted), or by adding a hyperlink back to any page on the BIM Dictionary.

Using the BIM Dictionary logo on a website or to promote an event are however subject to additional consideration and a **written permission** must be sought from the Head Editor before the logo can be used. In principle, a permission to use the BIM Dictionary logo may be granted if there is a public benefit from the website (e.g. it is a terminology page on a university's website), event (e.g. it is a knowledge-sharing site), or printed materials seeking to use the logo. The decision to grant a permission will be made on a case-by-case basis using a simple application form. For more information, please [Contact Us](#).

XIII. Note Covering Intellectual Property

BIM Dictionary Items are provided to all users free of charge under a [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License](#). All contributions by Editors will fall under the same open license (Editors cannot claim copyright on original or translated material). Permissions beyond providing open and free access to BIM Dictionary Items are governed by applicable laws (Australia, State of Victoria), BIM Excellence Privacy Policy, Terms of Use and relevant Licensing Arrangements.

XIV. More Info

To stay informed of the Initiative's main activities, new tools and publications, please subscribe to the [Mailing List](#) and/or follow us on Twitter ([@BIMInitiative](#)) and on [LinkedIn](#). Also please follow and share your thoughts with the teams using the [#BIMdictionary](#) and [#BIMInitiative](#) hashtags. To request more information, suggest an improvement or to simply get in touch, please [Contact Us](#).

XV. Change Log

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION
0.1	Aug 27, 2015	Initial draft
0.2-0.4	Sep '16 – Jan '17	Renamed document to BIM Dictionary Editor's Guide - Aligned with 100 Series
1.0	Jan 18, 2017	First Official Version for release through BIMexcellence.org
1.1	Apr 3, 2017	Minor changes
1.2	Mar 25, 2018	Responsibilities clarified + text updated to match new available features
2.0	Sep 4, 2019	Updated to correspond with the new BIM Dictionary Platform and new roles
2.1	Oct 15, 2019	Typos + updated Language Reviewer role